

- N. R. EL-RAYYES and H. M. RAMDAN, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1987, **24**, 589; R. M. DODSON and J. K. SEYLER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, **16**, 461; A. L. WEIS, V. M. SHIRINA and V. P. MAMARV, *Izv. Sib Otd. Akad. Nauk SSSR, Ser Khim Nauk*, 1975, 144 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, **84**, 105528).
- N. R. EL-RAYYES and H. M. RAMDAN, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1987, **24**, 1141.
- S. S. MEHAR, S. NAIK, R. K. BEHERA and A. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 274.
- H. M. RANDAL, R. G. FOWLER, N. FUSON and J. R. DANGLE, "Infrared Determination of Organic Structures", Van Nostrand, New York, 1949.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 4th. ed., ELBS, London, 1978, p. 796
- T. E. ACHARY, P. N. DHAL and A. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1204

1

Heptacos-3-en-25-one—A New Unsaturated Ketone from *Ajuga bracteosa*†

R. S. BHAKUNI, Y. N. SHUKLA* and R. S. THAKUR

Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants,
Lucknow-226 016

Manuscript received 4 September 1989, accepted 6 December 1989

AJUGA bracteosa (Labiateae) is a perennial herb occurring in Western Himalayas from Kashmir to Nepal^{1,2}. The leaves are diuretic, stimulant¹ and used as a substitute for Cinchona³. The plant is also reported to possess cardiostimulant action in animals⁴ and anticancer activity in rats and mice⁵. Previous work on this plant includes isolation of saturated and unsaturated acids⁶, insect antifeedant diterpenes^{7,8} and insecticidal diterpenes⁹. In continuation of our work on the aerial parts of this plant¹⁰, we now report a new unsaturated ketone.

The air-dried powdered aerial parts of *A. bracteosa* were extracted with *n*-hexane and the extract was concentrated under reduced pressure which in turn was subjected to vacuum liquid chromatography (VLC)¹¹ using silica gel as adsorbant. Compound **1** was eluted in hexane and was found to be homogenous on tlc, **1** m.p. 70–71°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1610, 820 (unsaturation), 1710 (keto function), 1380 (CH₃) and 715, 710 cm⁻¹ (straight chain); *m/z* 392 corresponding to C₂₇H₅₂O. The base peak at *m/z* 57 and other abundant ion at *m/z* 335 formed by the α -fission of the CO group located it at C-25 whereas the other characteristic ions at *m/z* 363, 337 and 55 established the position of the double bond at C-3. These fragmentations are depicted on the structure. These data suggested the structure of **1** as heptacos-3-en-25-one which is in full accord with its ¹H nmr spectrum (80 MHz; CDCl₃) displaying resonances at δ 0.90 (6H, t, *J* 8Hz, two terminal CH₃), 2.35 (4H, t, *J* 8Hz, two CH₂ adjacent to CO function), 5.32 (2H, t, *J* 6Hz, olefinic function), 1.60 (4H, m, two CH₂ adjacent to double bond) and 1.25 (36H, brs, eighteen CH₂ of chain).

†CIMAP communication no. 16/89.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to R.S.I.C. at C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for recording the mass spectrum.

References

- "The Wealth of India—Raw Materials", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1948, Vol. I, p. 42.
- R. K. GUPTA, "Flora Nainitalensis", Navyug Traders, New Delhi, 1968, p. 273.
- R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 10.
- D. G. PATIL, O. D. GULATI and S. D. GOKHLE, *Indian J. Physiol Pharmacol.*, 1962, **6**, 224.
- M. L. DHAR, B. N. DHAWAN, B. N. MEHROTRA and O. RAY, *Indian J. Exp Biol.*, 1968, **6**, 232.
- D. S. BHAKUNI and K. N. KAUL, *J. Sci. Ind Res, Sect B*, 1961, **20**, 185.
- I. KUBO, L. YUE-WHEI, V. BALOGH-NAIR, K. NAKANISHI and A. OHAPYO, *J. Chem. Soc. Chem Commun.*, 1976, 949.
- I. KUBO, M. KIDO and Y. FUKUYAMA, *J. Chem Soc Chem Commun.*, 1980, 897.
- I. KUBO, J. A. KLOCKE, I. MIURA and Y. FUKUYAMA, *J. Chem Soc. Chem. Commun.*, 1982, 618.
- R. S. BHAKUNI, Y. N. SHUKLA and R. S. THAKUR, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1987, **49**, 225.
- S. W. PELLETIER, H. P. CHOKSHI and H. K. DESAI, *J. Natural Prod.*, 1986, **49**, 892.

Rapid Tlc Separation of Aromatic Amines on Surfactant Impregnated Silica Gel-G Plates

RAJEEV JAIN* and ASHA BHATIA

Department of Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011

Manuscript received 22 May 1989, accepted 21 November 1989

AROMATIC amines are of considerable importance in industrial, toxicological and pharmaceutical applications¹. Keeping this in view tlc separation and detection of various aromatic amines have been carried out by several workers on various adsorbents². Duncan *et al.*³ analysed aromatic amines by tlc on cellulose impregnated with bis-(2-ethylhexyl)hydrogen phosphate. Yasuda⁴ carried